

ISic2787

I.Sicily inscription 2787

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

volcanic (local stone, from Fuardo)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lipara

Place of origin (modern)

Lipari

Provenance

Contr. Diana

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lipari, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Eoliano "Luigi Bernabò Brea", inventory 13840

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI333204

1. Ζωπυρίσκος
2. Ἡρακλείδ ο,υ
3. Συρακόσιος,ς.
- 4.

Edition: PHI334271

1. Ζωπυρίσ κ,ο,ς
2. Ἡρακλεί [δα]
3. Συρακόσ,ι,ο-
4. ς.
- 5.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645184

PHI 333204

PHI 334271

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